

INTERACTION OF TRANSVERSE CRACKS OF FINITE SIZE IN A CROSS-PLY LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

While the formation of, and the effects on properties, of fully developed transverse cracks in $[0/90]_n$ laminates has been the subject of extensive investigation, there has been very little consideration of the effects of crack size and interaction on the initiation of unstable transverse crack growth from pre-existing relatively small defects. The objective is to summarise recent progress that has been made developing a complex variable technique that can be used to calculate the effective stress intensity factors for bridged systems of transverse cracks, having lengths shorter than the laminate width, in the 90° plies of $[0/90]_n$ laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Anisotropic materials such as carbon-fibre-reinforced plastic (CFRP) or glass-reinforced plastic (GRP), are in common use in the aerospace, defence and general engineering sectors, due to their high stiffness, strength and damage tolerance. They are often implemented as laminates in order to provide tensile strength in two orthogonal directions. When subjected to an axial tensile stress, the 90° plies tend to form transverse cracks parallel to the fibres such that the crack density increases with the applied load. Such cracking may also occur during the manufacturing process itself because of thermal expansion mismatch between plies having differing orientations. Transverse cracking is the most significant mechanism contributing to the onset of damage within the laminate, and to subsequent damage growth as the load is further increased or during fatigue loading. In this paper, one method is examined for determining the stress and displacement fields around the relatively small cracks that represent the defects in the 90° ply of a $[0/90]_n$ laminate that will grow, in some cases following crack coalescence, into fully developed transverse cracks as the laminate is loaded. From the stress field the stress intensity factors for the cracks are readily found. The method considered is able to take account of the interaction of the small defects with their neighbours, and with fully developed transverse cracks that have already formed. Predictions for the stress intensity factors will be of particular value when considering the growth of transverse cracks in laminates during fatigue loading.

The theory presented here, and that in a more detailed publication [1], extends earlier work (McCartney and Gorley [2]) in which the interaction of *inclined unbridged* cracks in a thin plate of *isotropic* material was considered. This paper is concerned with the case of *parallel bridged* transverse cracks embedded in an *anisotropic* [0/90]_s cross-ply laminate.

STRESS AND DISPLACEMENT FIELDS AROUND A SINGLE CRACK

Stress-strain relations

Generalised plane stress conditions are assumed, with the axial loading direction parallel to the y-axis. An anisotropic thin plate is assumed having the following stress-strain relations

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx} &= a_{11}\sigma_{xx} + a_{12}\sigma_{yy}, \\ \epsilon_{yy} &= a_{12}\sigma_{xx} + a_{22}\sigma_{yy}, \\ 2\epsilon_{xy} &= a_{66}\sigma_{xy}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where} \quad a_{11} = \frac{1}{E_T}, \quad a_{22} = \frac{1}{E_A}, \quad a_{12} = -\frac{\nu_A}{E_A}, \quad a_{66} = \frac{1}{\mu_A}. \quad (2)$$

For a [0/90]_s cross-ply laminate the values of E_A and E_T (the axial and transverse Young's moduli), ν_A (the axial Poisson's ratio) and μ_A (the axial shear modulus) are either prescribed or calculated from single ply properties using standard methods.

A representation for stress and displacement fields

Consider first of all a single straight through-crack of length $2c$ embedded within an infinite plate so that the crack plane is normal to the surfaces of the plate. For the assumed conditions of generalised plane stress, crack problems are two dimensional. Introduce rectangular Cartesian coordinates (x, y) such that the crack is parallel to the x-axis and occupies the region $|x - a| \leq c, y = b$. The complex variable z is introduced such that $z = x + iy$. The stress and displacement representation developed by Sih and Liebowitz [3] is used here, which is valid for generalised plane strain deformations in rectilinearly anisotropic bodies containing a crack. The representation involves two analytic functions $\phi(z_1)$ and $\psi(z_2)$ of the complex variables

$$z_1 = x - a + s_1(y - b), \quad z_2 = x - a + s_2(y - b), \quad (3)$$

where s_1 and s_2 are the two roots (having positive imaginary parts) of the quartic equation

$$a_{11}s^4 + (2a_{12} + a_{66})s^2 + a_{22} = 0. \quad (4)$$

The representation for the stress components is given by

$$\sigma_{xx} = \text{Re} [s_1^2 \phi'(z_1) + s_2^2 \psi'(z_2)] , \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = \text{Re} [\phi'(z_1) + \psi'(z_2)] , \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = - \text{Re} [s_1 \phi'(z_1) + s_2 \psi'(z_2)] , \quad (7)$$

and that for the displacement components is

$$u = \text{Re} [p_1 \phi(z_1) + p_2 \psi(z_2)] , \quad (8)$$

$$v = \text{Re} [q_1 \phi(z_1) + q_2 \psi(z_2)] , \quad (9)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} p_k &= a_{11} s_k^2 + a_{12} \\ q_k &= a_{12} s_k + a_{22} / s_k \end{aligned} \right\} \text{ for } k = 1, 2 . \quad (10)$$

The stress and displacement representation automatically satisfies the equilibrium equations and the stress-strain relations (1) for any analytic functions $\phi(z)$ and $\psi(z)$ of the complex variable z . Let $\zeta = \xi + i\eta$, $t_1 = a - c + ib$, $t_2 = a + c + ib$

$$\text{where } \zeta = \zeta(z) = \frac{2z - (t_1 + t_2)}{t_2 - t_1} . \quad (11)$$

The crack of length $2c$, centred at the point $z = a + ib$, is then described by $-1 < \xi < 1$, $\eta = 0$ and the following Cauchy integral representation is used

$$\phi'(z) \equiv \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\rho(\xi)}{\sqrt{1 - \xi^2}} \frac{d\xi}{\zeta(z) - \xi} , \quad (12)$$

$$\psi'(z) \equiv \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sigma(\xi)}{\sqrt{1 - \xi^2}} \frac{d\xi}{\zeta(z) - \xi} , \quad (13)$$

where the functions $\rho(\xi)$ and $\sigma(\xi)$ satisfy the following conditions

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\rho(\xi) d\xi}{\sqrt{1 - \xi^2}} = 0 , \quad \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sigma(\xi) d\xi}{\sqrt{1 - \xi^2}} = 0 , \quad (14)$$

ensuring that the representation leads to the closure of the crack at the tips $x - a = \pm c$.

Chebyshev polynomial expansion

Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind are defined over the interval $[-1, 1]$ by

$$T_n(\cos \alpha) \equiv \cos n\alpha, \quad 0 \leq \alpha \leq \pi, \quad n \geq 0. \quad (15)$$

Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind are defined by

$$U_n(\cos \alpha) = \frac{\sin(n+1)\alpha}{\sin \alpha}, \quad 0 \leq \alpha \leq \pi, \quad n \geq 0. \quad (16)$$

The functions $\rho(\xi)$ and $\sigma(\xi)$ are then assumed to have the form

$$\rho(\xi) = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n T_n(\xi), \quad \sigma(\xi) = \sum_{n=1}^N B_n T_n(\xi), \quad (17)$$

where A_n and B_n are complex coefficients. The crack closure conditions (14) are automatically satisfied and on substituting in (12) and (13)

$$\phi'(z) \equiv \sum_{n=1}^N A_n H_n(\zeta), \quad \psi'(z) \equiv \sum_{n=1}^N B_n H_n(\zeta), \quad (18)$$

where, using a result established by Gladwell and England [4],

$$H_n(\zeta) \equiv \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{T_n(\xi) d\xi}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2} \zeta - \xi} \equiv \frac{[\zeta - (\zeta^2 - 1)^{1/2}]^n}{(\zeta^2 - 1)^{1/2}}, \quad n \geq 0. \quad (19)$$

By selecting the branch of $(\zeta^2 - 1)^{1/2}$ which is asymptotic to ζ as $|\zeta| \rightarrow \infty$, it can be shown that for $n \geq 1$,

$$H_n(\zeta) \equiv \frac{[\zeta - (\zeta^2 - 1)^{1/2}]^n}{(\zeta^2 - 1)^{1/2}} \equiv \frac{T_n(\zeta)}{(\zeta^2 - 1)^{1/2}} - U_{n-1}(\zeta). \quad (20)$$

Traction distribution on the crack

Let S_n^+ , S_t^+ , S_n^- , S_t^- be the normal and transverse tractions on the upper and lower surfaces of the crack. It has been shown [2] using (6), (7), (18) and (20) that for $|\xi| < 1$ the following simple expression is valid for the tractions on the crack surfaces:

$$(S_n^\pm + i S_t^\pm)(\xi) = - \sum_{n=1}^N (\alpha_n + i \beta_n) U_{n-1}(\xi), \quad |\xi| < 1, \quad (21)$$

where $\alpha_n = A_n + B_n, \quad \beta_n = -(s_1 A_n + s_2 B_n),$

are real coefficients.

Displacement discontinuity across the crack

It has been shown [2] from (8), (9), (18) and (20) that the displacement discontinuities across the crack are given by

$$\Delta v(\xi) \equiv (V_n^+ - V_n^-)(\xi) = 4c\sqrt{a_{22}g} \sqrt{1 - \xi^2} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\alpha_n}{n} U_{n-1}(\xi), \quad (22)$$

$$\Delta u(\xi) \equiv (U_i^+ - U_i^-)(\xi) = 4c\sqrt{a_{11}g} \sqrt{1 - \xi^2} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\beta_n}{n} U_{n-1}(\xi), \quad (23)$$

where
$$g = \frac{1}{4} \left(2\sqrt{a_{11}a_{22}} + 2a_{12} + a_{66} \right). \quad (24)$$

Stress intensity factors

It has been shown [2] that the stress intensity factors at the crack tip at $x = -c$ are given by

$$K_I^1 + iK_{II}^1 = \sqrt{\pi c} \sum_{n=1}^N (-1)^{n+1} (\alpha_n + i\beta_n), \quad (25)$$

and the stress intensity factors at the crack tip at $x = c$ are given by

$$K_I^2 + iK_{II}^2 = \sqrt{\pi c} \sum_{n=1}^N (\alpha_n + i\beta_n). \quad (26)$$

MULTIPLE BRIDGED CRACK PROBLEMS

The analysis described above offers an elegant method of solving interacting crack problems because the relations (5-9), (18) and (20) enable the stress field of a crack to be calculated efficiently at all points in the cracked plate, and because the expressions for the stress intensity factors (25) and (26) are exceedingly simple in form. Interacting crack problems are solved by superimposing solutions having the structure described above for each of the cracks present (details given in [1]). Crack interaction effects arise when applying boundary conditions that must be satisfied at each crack location, provided that the cracks are close enough for such interaction effects to occur. Transverse cracks embedded in a cross-ply laminate will not behave as stress-free through-cracks as stress is transferred across the planes containing transverse cracks because of the presence of the neighbouring 0° plies. For mode I crack opening, this type of bridging for an isolated crack has been modelled [5], resulting in a crack bridging relation where the effective bridging tractions are linearly related to the crack opening displacement. It is now assumed that for both mode I and mode II crack opening the crack bridging relation for each crack has the form

$$(p + iq)(\xi) = [\Lambda \Delta v(\xi) + \sigma_1] + i[\mu \Delta u(\xi) + \tau_1], \quad (27)$$

where $p(\xi)$ and $q(\xi)$ are respectively the effective normal and shear bridging tractions acting at the point ξ on the crack surface, where $\Delta u(\xi)$ and $\Delta v(\xi)$ are the corresponding normal and tangential displacement discontinuities, and where Λ and μ are dimensionless parameters that depend upon the properties of the laminate. The parameters σ_i and τ_i are the values of the stresses $p(\xi)$ and $q(\xi)$ needed to *just* close the crack. These parameters are non-zero only when account is taken of thermal expansion mis-match effects between the 0° and 90° plies arising when the stress-free temperature $\Delta T \neq 0$. For the mode I opening mode the parameters Λ and σ_i are defined in [5] in terms of the geometry and properties of the laminate plies. When m interacting transverse cracks are considered the superimposition of the representation for the stress field relating to each crack present, and the application of the crack boundary conditions (27), leads (see [1] for details) to relations of the following type that must be satisfied for $s = 1 \dots m$ and all values $|\xi| < 1$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{yy}^0 + \sum_{r=1}^m \sum_{n=1}^{N_r} \left(\alpha_n^r \operatorname{Re} \left[H_n(\zeta_1^r) - s_1 \Delta H_n(\zeta_1^r, \zeta_2^r) \right] - \beta_n^r \operatorname{Re} \left[\Delta H_n(\zeta_1^r, \zeta_2^r) \right] \right) \\ - 4\Lambda c_s \sqrt{a_{22} g} \sqrt{1 - \xi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{N_r} \frac{\alpha_n^r}{n} U_{n-1}(\xi) - \sigma_i = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xy}^0 + \sum_{r=1}^m \sum_{n=1}^{N_r} \left(\alpha_n^r \operatorname{Re} \left[s_1 s_2 \Delta H_n(\zeta_1^r, \zeta_2^r) \right] + \beta_n^r \operatorname{Re} \left[H_n(\zeta_1^r) + s_2 \Delta H_n(\zeta_1^r, \zeta_2^r) \right] \right) \\ - 4\mu c_s \sqrt{a_{11} g} \sqrt{1 - \xi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{N_r} \frac{\beta_n^r}{n} U_{n-1}(\xi) - \tau_i = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$\text{where } \Delta H(\zeta_1, \zeta_2) = \frac{H_n(\zeta_1) - H_n(\zeta_2)}{s_1 - s_2}, \quad \text{and } \zeta_k = \xi + s_k \eta, \quad k = 1, 2, \quad (30)$$

and where σ_{xy}^0 , σ_{yy}^0 are the values of the stress components at the crack locations before the cracks formed. In (28) and (29) the superscript r refers the variables to the r^{th} crack where N_r Chebyshev terms are used for representation (17) for $\rho(\xi)$ and $\sigma(\xi)$ associated with the r^{th} crack. The relations (28) and (29) are used to derive a set of linear algebraic equations for the coefficients α_n^r , β_n^r , $r = 1 \dots N_r$, $r = 1 \dots m$ by satisfying exactly the relations (28) and (29) at a set of discrete points on the crack surfaces. The corresponding stress intensity factors for bridged interacting cracks $K = (\sigma - \sigma_i) \sqrt{\pi c_o} \phi$ are calculated using (25) and (26) applied to each of the cracks present where ϕ is independent of the uniaxial applied stress σ and depends only on the crack tip being examined and the geometry of the cracks. By applying a fracture criterion of the form $K = K_{IC}$ where K_{IC} is the effective fracture toughness of the composite (see [1, 5] for details), it can be shown that the transverse cracking stress σ_T is given by

$$(\sigma_T - \sigma_i) / \sigma_o = 1 / \phi, \quad (31)$$

where σ_o and c_o are normalising parameters such that $K_{IC} = \sigma_o \sqrt{\pi c_o}$. They are determined

from the properties of the plies in the laminate, laminate geometry and fracture toughness for the 90° ply (or fracture energy), using the methods described in [1, 5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following values of the thermoelastic constants assumed for calculations are for a typical [0/90]_s carbon fibre epoxy cross-ply laminate where the thickness of the plies have the same value:

$$E_A = E_T = 75.1 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu_A = 0.033, \quad \mu_A = 4.59 \text{ GPa}.$$

An isolated transverse crack in a cross-ply laminate is first considered where the crack bridging law (27) is applied for the case of axial loading. The parameter Λ appearing in (27) is calculated in terms of the thermoelastic constants using relations specified in [1, 5], and the parameter $\sigma_i = 0$ as the stress-free difference ΔT is assumed here to be zero. The number of collocation points for each crack was selected to be $N_s = 80$ (for all s); a much larger number than is needed for unbridged cracks. The transverse cracking stress was calculated using (31) and the results are shown as discrete solid diamond points in Fig.1 where the normalised cracking stress $(\sigma_T - \sigma_i)/\sigma_0$ is plotted as a function of the normalised crack length c/c_0 .

The isolated bridged crack problem can be solved by other methods [5] involving the numerical solution of an integral equation. Such solutions generate the continuous curve shown in Fig.1. The continuous curve agrees extremely well with the discrete values generated by applying to an isolated crack the multiple crack theory derived in this paper. The stress required to initiate the unstable growth of a transverse crack reduces to an asymptotic limit $\sqrt{(\pi/2)}$ as the crack length increases, shown as a dotted line in Fig.1. The transverse cracking stress is thus effectively independent of the crack length whenever $c/c_0 > 5$. It is worth noting that this asymptotic limit was used as the fracture criterion for the study of non-uniform progressive crack formation in a cross-ply laminate subject to biaxial loading [6]. As pointed out by McCartney [5] it is important to note that the continuous curve shown in Fig.1 is a master curve that applies to *all* [0/90]_s laminates and for *all* values of the stress-free temperature ΔT ; the effect of ply properties and of thermal residual stresses being accounted for in the definitions of normalised stress and normalised crack length through the parameters σ_i , σ_0 and c_0 .

In order to illustrate crack interaction effects, two collinear bridged cracks are considered. They are assumed to have the same length $2c$ and the separation of nearest neighbour crack tips is denoted by $2d$. Two crack separations are considered given by the values $d/c = 0.1$ and $d/c = 0.5$. The crack problem has been solved by the methods described above, and the stress to *initiate* growth at the nearest neighbour crack tips calculated using (31). The results are shown as discrete points (open symbols) in Fig.1. The closer the crack tips, the lower the cracking stress. For long crack lengths where $c/c_0 > 5$, the effect of crack interaction on cracking stress is limited because of the effect of bridging. The curves are seen to be monotonic increasing at longer cracks lengths. This does not imply stable growth as the ratio d/c changes when crack growth takes place. Many other types of crack interaction can be analysed using the methodology described in this paper, including the interaction of a small transverse crack with fully developed cracks that already have formed traversing the entire width of the laminate. A discussion of such interactions is, however, beyond the scope of this short paper.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The results presented arose from participation in Phase II of the PREDICT project (Prediction of Damage Initiation and Growth in Composite Materials) which is a collaboration between British Aerospace (Sowerby Research Centre), Ciba Composites, Tenax Fibers, National Physical Laboratory, DRA (Farnborough), University of Bristol and the University of Surrey. The project, led by British Aerospace, is funded under the LINK Structural Composites programme of the DTI's Research and Technology Initiative (IED Grant Ref. RA 6/25/01).

FIG.1 : Dependence of normalised crack initiation stress on normalised crack length for bridged transverse cracks in a crossply laminate.